

Bu yerda $\varphi(M_{ks})$ quyidagi algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini qanoatlantiradi:

$$\varphi(M_{js}) = f(M_{js}) + \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N K(M_{js}, M_{ks}) \varphi(M_{ks}) \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, N)$$

Va $\varphi_k(P)$ (5) formula orqali aniqlanadi.

Teoremani isbotlashdan oldin quyidagi lemmani keltiramiz. Faraz qilaylik:

$$\Delta(\lambda) = \begin{vmatrix} 1 - \frac{\lambda}{n} K(M_{1s}, M_{1s}) \Phi_1(M_{1s}) & \dots & -\frac{\lambda}{n} K(M_{1s}, M_{ns}) \Phi_n(M_{1s}) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ -\frac{\lambda}{n} K(M_{ns}, M_{1s}) \Phi_1(M_{ns}) & \dots & 1 - \frac{\lambda}{n} K(M_{ns}, M_{ns}) \Phi_n(M_{ns}) \end{vmatrix} \quad (6)$$

1 -lemma

Agar $K(P, Q) \in E_{2s}^a(C_2)$ bo'lsa va $D(\lambda) \neq 0$ hamda $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon(n) = 0$ shartlari bajarilsa, shuningdek, M_{ks} nuqtalar shunday tanlansa-ki, $F \in E_s^a$, unda quyidagi kvadratur formula o'rinlidir:

$$\int_{G_s} F(P) dP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n F(M_{ks}) + o(\varepsilon(n)) \quad (7)$$

shunda yetarlicha katta n uchun quyidagi baholash o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$|\Delta(\lambda)| \geq \frac{1}{2} |D\lambda|$$

1- teorema ning isboti:

Birinchi navbatda, (1) tenglamaning yechimi $E_s^a(C_5)$ sinfiga tegishli ekanligini ko'rsatamiz, bu yerda

$$C_5 = C + \left(3 + \frac{2}{a-1}\right)^{2s} |\lambda| C_2 B_1$$

Haqiqatan ham,

$$C_5(m_1, \dots, m_s)$$

ifoda orqali Furrye koeffitsientlarni kiritamiz $\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_s) - f(x_1, \dots, x_s)$. (1) tenglamadan quyidagi hosila kelib chiqadi:

$$\begin{aligned} C_5(m_1, \dots, m_s) &= \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 [\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_s) - f(x_1, \dots, x_s)] \times \\ &\times e^{-2\pi i(m_1 x_1 + \dots + m_s x_s)} dx_1 \dots dx_s = \\ &\lambda \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \left[\varphi(y_1, \dots, y_s) \left(\int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \prod_{j=1}^s ctg \pi(x_j - y_j) K(x_1, \dots, x_s, y_1, \dots, y_s) e^{2\pi i(m_1 x_1 + \dots + m_s x_s)} dx_1 \dots dx_s \right) \right] dy_1 \dots dy_s \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Shartga ko'ra $K(P, Q) \in E_s^a(C_2)$, shuning uchun

$$|K(P, Q)| = \left| \sum_{m_1, \dots, m_{2s} = -\infty}^{\infty} C_2(m_1, \dots, m_{2s}) e^{2\pi i(m_1 x_1 + \dots + m_s x_s)} \right| \leq C_2 \sum_{m_1, \dots, m_{2s} = -\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(m_1 \dots m_s)^a} =$$

$$C_2 \left(1 + 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^a}\right)^{2s} \leq \left(3 + \frac{2}{a-1}\right)^{2s} C_2 \quad (9)$$

Tenglikni s marta qo'llab, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \prod_{j=1}^s ctg \pi(x_j - y_j) e^{2\pi i(m_1 y_1 + \dots + m_s y_s)} dy_1 \dots dy_s = \\ &= i^s \operatorname{sign}(m_1 \dots m_s) e^{2\pi i(m_1 x_1 + \dots + m_s x_s)} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

(4), (9) va (10) tengliklaridan quyidagini hosil qilamiz: Ushbu natija orqali

$$|C_5(m_1, \dots, m_s)| \leq \left(\lambda \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 [\varphi(y_1, \dots, y_s) \prod_{j=1}^s K(x_1, \dots, x_s, y_1, \dots, y_s) \times \sum_{j=1}^s \operatorname{ctg} \pi(x_j - y_j) e^{2\pi i(m_1 x_1 + \dots + m_s x_s)} dx_1 \dots dx_s] \right) \leq (3 + \frac{2}{a-1})^{2s} |\lambda| C_2 \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 |\varphi(y_1, \dots, y_s)| dy_1 \dots dy_s \leq (3 + \frac{2}{a-1})^{2s} |\lambda| A_1 C_2$$

va quyidagini e'tiborga olamiz $f(P) \in E_s^\alpha(C_1)$. 1-lemmaga muvofiq quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\varphi(P) = \varphi(P) - f(P) + f(P) \in E_s^\alpha(C_1 + (3 + \frac{2}{a-1})^{2s} |\lambda| A_1 C_2)$$

2-lemma. a_1, \dots, a_n N modulli β indeksli optimal koeffitsientlar bo'lsin. Agar $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ funksiya E_n^α sinfga tegishli bo'lsa, u holda

$$\int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 f(x_1, \dots, x_n) dx_1 \dots dx_n \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N f\left(\left\{\frac{a_1 k}{N}\right\}, \dots, \left\{\frac{a_n k}{N}\right\}\right)$$

kubatur formulaning $R_N[f]$ qoldiq hadi uchun

$$|R_N[f]| \leq CC' N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta} N,$$

baho o'rinli bo'ladi, bunda

$$C' = C_0^\alpha + nB^n, \quad B = 3 + \frac{2}{\alpha - 1}.$$

2-lemmaga binoan, agar $K(P, Q)$ funksiyasi integrallash o'zgaruvchilari bo'yicha qaralganda $E_s^\alpha(C_2)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsa, unda 1-lemmadan foydalanib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$K(P, Q)\varphi(Q)$ ham $E_s^\alpha(C_6)$ sinfga tegishli, bu yerda:

$$(C_6) = AC_2(C_1 + (3 + \frac{2}{a-1})^{2s} |\lambda| A_1 C_2), \quad A \leq (2^{\alpha+1} (3 + \frac{2}{a-1}))^s$$

va quyidagini yozish mumkin:

$$\varphi(P) = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N K(P, M_k) \varphi(M_k) \Phi_k(P) + f(P) + R, \quad R \leq A_3(a, n) C_5 N^{-\alpha} \ln^{\alpha\beta} N \quad (11)$$

bunda qoldiq had R quyidagicha baholanadi:

$$R \leq A_3(a, n) C_5 N^{-\alpha} \ln^{\alpha\beta} N$$

Bu yerda:

$$A_3(a, n) = \{9^n A^2 (C_0^\alpha + s(3 + \frac{2}{a-1})^s)^2 C_6^2 + \frac{(2a)^{n+1}}{(2a-1)^n}\}.$$

Agar bu natijani $P=M_j$ ($j=1, 2, \dots, N$) nuqtalar uchun yozsak:

$$\varphi(M)_j = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N K(M_j, M_k) \varphi(M_k) \varphi_k(M_j) + f(M_j) + R_j.$$

Shundan keyin, ushbu ifodadan quyidagi natijani hosil qilamiz:

$$\varphi(M)_j = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N K(M_j, M_k) \varphi(M_k) \varphi_k(M_j) + f(M_j)$$

N ni n ga almashtirgandan so'ng va quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz

$$z_j = \varphi(M_j) - \varphi'_k(M_j), \quad a_{jk} = -\frac{\lambda}{N} K(M_j, M_k) \varphi_k(M_j), \quad b_j R_j. \quad (12)$$

Bu esa quyidagi chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini hosil qiladi:

$$b_j + \sum_{k=1}^n a_{jk} z_k = (b_j) \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

Determinantlarni kiritamiz:

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 1 + a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 1 + a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} \quad \Delta_k = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + a_{11} & \dots & a_{1,k-1} & b_1 & a_{1,k+1} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & \dots & a_{n,k-1} & b_n & a_{n,k+1} & \dots & 1 + a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{Natijada:}$$

$$z_k = \frac{\Delta_k}{\Delta} \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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